

Studies of Biologically Active Quinazolones : Synthesis of Some Newer Variously Substituted 4-Quinazolones as Antifertility Agents

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In view of the diverse biological activities associated with quinazolones, some 2,3-disubstituted, 2,3,6 or 2,3,7-tri-substituted and 2,3,6,7-tetra-substituted quinazolones have been synthesized starting from the corresponding anthranilic acids, phenoxy acid chlorides and amines. The antifertility activity of these compounds is under study.

DIVERSE biological activities have been encountered in compounds having the quinazolone ring system, such as CNS¹, hypnotic², anticonvulsant^{3,4} and analgesic⁵ etc.

Furthermore, it has been recently shown that quinazolones also possess antifertility activity⁷. Antifertility activity might be associated with phoxymethylene group and isopropyl, pyridyl at position 2 and 3 in quinazolone moiety. In view of these observations, it was thought to synthesize some newer quinazolone derivatives and study their antifertility activity.

In general, the quinazolones were prepared by the reaction of different heterocyclic amines with substituted anthranilis which in turn was obtained by the reaction of substituted phenoxy acid chlorides with substituted anthranilic acids in pyridine solution.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

Synthesis of substituted anthranilic acids :

The anthranilic acids were synthesized by the method reported in literature^{7,8}.

Synthesis of substituted anthranils :

Equimolar (.01 mole) ratio of substituted anthranilic acids and phenoxy acid chlorides⁹ were taken in pyridine solution (50 ml) at a temperature below 10°, stirred well and cooled. A solid mass separated which was filtered and washed with ice cold water. Their melting points and percentage composition of C and N are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R	Molecular formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	Carbon %		N %	
							Calculated	Found	Calculated	Found
1.	H	H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ NO ₂	67	220	67.84	67.79	4.74	4.725
2.	Br	Br	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Br ₂ NO ₂	64	270	48.58	48.521	3.17	3.158
3.	H	I	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ INO ₂	59	230	46.94	46.92	3.42	3.41
4.	H	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClNO ₂	66	241	61.43	61.41	4.77	4.76
5.	Br	Br	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClBr ₂ NO ₂	70	189	40.45	40.435	3.14	3.135
6.	H	I	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₅ H ₉ ClINO ₂	54	245	43.5	43.45	3.38	3.372
7.	H	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂	63	234	62.68	62.67	10.44	10.432

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R	Z	Molecular formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	Carbon%		Nitrogen%	
1.	H	H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	2-Thiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	56	180	66.98	66.96	10.12	10.99
2.	H	H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	2-Pyridyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	55	160	70.19	70.185	11.70	11.66
3.	H	H	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	4-Pyridyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	57	205	70.19	70.18	11.70	11.68
4.	Br	Br	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	2-Thiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	65	145	48.59	48.57	8.03	8.29
5.	H	I	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	2-Thiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ IN ₂ O ₂ S	60	190	46.49	46.42	8.55	8.53
6.	H	I	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	2-Pyridyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ IN ₃ O ₂	58	198	53.73	53.72	8.95	8.948
7.	Br	Br	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	2-Pyridyl	C ₁₁ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂	59	195	48.7	48.69	8.12	8.119
8.	H	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	2-Pyridyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	66	150	67.4	67.95	15.6	15.56
9.	H	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	4-Pyridyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	68	158	67.4	67.96	15.6	15.58
10.	H	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	2-Thiazolyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	59	148	59.34	59.32	15.38	15.29
11.	Br	Br	<i>o</i> -Cl	2-Thiazolyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ClBr ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	70	155	40.9	40.85	10.62	10.61
12.	Br	Br	<i>o</i> -Cl	2-Pyridyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ClBr ₂ N ₃ O ₂	71	131	46.06	46.04	8.06	8.05
13.	H	I	<i>o</i> -Cl	2-Pyridyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ClIN ₃ O ₂	54	172	49.07	49.06	8.58	8.57
14.	H	I	<i>o</i> -Cl	2-Thiazolyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ClIN ₂ O ₂ S	68	201	43.54	43.52	8.467	8.461
15.	H	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	2-Thiazolyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	61	197	55.5	55.47	11.47	11.465
16.	H	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	2-Pyridyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ClN ₃ O ₂	64	185	66.11	66.109	11.5	11.492

Synthesis of Quinazolones :

Quinazolones were synthesized by refluxing equimolar proportion of substituted anthranils with heterocyclic amine in benzene. Excess of solvent was removed by distillation. The resulting residue was washed with water. The solid was crystallized with suitable solvent (Table 2).

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References

- I. K. KARBUR and S. H. ZAHEER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 28, 334.
- M. L. GUJRAL, P. N. SAXENA and R. S. TEWARI, *Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1955, 43, 637.
- L. G. ZIE'BERMINTS, *Izv. Estestv.-Nauchn Inst. Perm'sk. Univ.* 1964, 14(7), 141-50; *Chem. Abs.*, 1966, 64, 1220.
- P. K. SETH and S. S. PARMAR *Can. J. Physiol. Pharmacol.*, 1965, 43, 1019.
- R. H. SELLER, M. FUEHS, G. ONESH, C. SWARTZ, A. N. BREST and J. H. MOYER, *Clin. Pharmacol. Therap.*, 1962, 3, 180.
- S. K. SAXENA and S. SOMASEKHARA, *Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1972, 60, 284.
- A. S. WHEELER and W. M. OATS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 32, 770.
- C. J. KLEMMER and J. H. HUNTER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 5, 227.
- J. W. WOOP and T. D. FONTAINE, (C.U.S. Bar of Agr. Belltrville) *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 89.